

Challenges and Opportunities in the Expanded Career Progression System for Teachers of Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal S.Y 2025-2026

Chin Chin Mae Magsino¹

1 – Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal; Golden Gate Colleges
chinchin.magsino@deped.gov.ph / 0009-0001-1585-3271

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the influence of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) on teachers' professional growth, motivation, and commitment, as well as the challenges they encounter in its implementation within the Division of Batangas. Specifically, it sought to determine teachers' perceptions of the opportunities provided by ECPS in terms of training, its impact on their motivation and professional commitment, their ability to balance ECPS tasks with classroom responsibilities, and the challenges faced in workload, requirements, evaluation system, and career mobility.

The study employed a descriptive research design, utilizing a structured questionnaire distributed among 40 teachers of Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal. Weighted mean and ranking were used to analyze the data. Data were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire that measured teachers' perceptions of ECPS in terms of training, promotion, recognition, skills development, and its impact on motivation and commitment, as well as the challenges encountered during implementation. The collected data were analyzed using weighted mean and ranking to determine the overall perception of the respondents.

Findings revealed that teachers strongly perceive ECPS as beneficial in promoting professional growth, particularly in terms of training, promotion, recognition, and skills development. The system was also found to positively influence teachers' motivation and professional commitment, as it encourages them to enhance their competencies, pursue higher learning, and remain dedicated to their profession. However, despite these positive outcomes, challenges were identified in terms of increased workload, extensive documentary requirements, and the need to balance ECPS-related tasks with classroom responsibilities.

The study concludes that while ECPS is an effective mechanism for enhancing teacher motivation, commitment, and professional growth, its successful implementation requires adequate institutional support. Strengthening administrative assistance, improving communication of guidelines, and providing workload management strategies are recommended to ensure that the system achieves its intended goals without overburdening teachers.

Keywords: *career progression, teacher motivation, professional development, ECPS, educational management*

1. Introduction

Education is widely recognized as a fundamental pillar of national development and social transformation, with teachers serving as the primary agents in delivering quality education and shaping the future of learners. The effectiveness of any educational system largely depends on the competence, motivation, and commitment of its teachers. As such, continuous professional development and clear career advancement pathways are essential in ensuring that teachers remain motivated and capable of meeting the evolving demands of education. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education has introduced various reforms to strengthen teacher development, one of which is the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS).

The ECPS was designed to address the limitations of the traditional career ladder by providing more inclusive, competency-based, and flexible pathways for teacher advancement. It allows teachers to progress horizontally within the teaching track or vertically into leadership roles, based on merit and demonstrated competencies aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). This system aims to enhance teacher motivation, promote professional growth, and recognize diverse contributions within the teaching profession.

Despite its promising objectives, the implementation of ECPS presents both opportunities and challenges at the school level. Teachers may benefit from increased access to professional development opportunities, recognition of their efforts, and clearer promotion pathways. However, they may also encounter difficulties such as increased workload, complex documentation requirements, and challenges in balancing ECPS demands with their teaching responsibilities. These concerns highlight the need to examine how the system is experienced by teachers in actual practice.

Several studies emphasize that career progression systems significantly influence teachers' motivation, job satisfaction, and professional commitment. When teachers perceive that their efforts are recognized and rewarded, they are more likely to remain engaged and committed to their profession. Conversely, unclear policies and excessive administrative demands may lead to stress and reduced effectiveness. Therefore, understanding teachers' perceptions of ECPS is crucial in determining whether the system achieves its intended goals.

This study aims to examine the challenges and opportunities brought about by the implementation of ECPS at Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How do teachers perceive the opportunities provided by the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) for their professional growth in terms of:

- 1.1 training,
- 1.2 promotion
- 1.3 recognition,
- 1.4 skills development?

2. In what ways does the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) influence teachers' motivation and commitment to the teaching profession

- 2.1 Implementation,
- 2.2 teacher motivation,
- 2.3 professional commitment?

3. How do teachers balance the demands of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) with their classroom responsibilities?

4. What in terms of: challenges do teachers encounter in the implementation of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) in relation to their teaching profession

- 4.1 workload,
- 4.2 requirements,
- 4.3 evaluation system,
- 4.4 career mobility?

5. Based on the findings, how can teachers' experiences and insights guide the development of school-level support systems for 31 the effective implementation of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS)?

2. Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design, specifically employing a mixed-method approach. The quantitative aspect will gather data through survey questionnaires to determine teachers' perceptions of the opportunities, challenges, and effects of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS). The qualitative aspect, through interviews or focus group discussions, will provide deeper insights into teachers' lived experiences and perspectives. This design is appropriate because it allows for both measurable data and narrative accounts that capture the complexity of the research problem.

Participants

The subject of this study were the 40 teachers from Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal who are directly affected by the Expanded Career Progression System. Purposive sampling employed, as they are in the best position to provide information on the challenges and opportunities in ECPS implementation. The study included teachers across grade levels and with varying years of teaching experience to ensure a comprehensive representation of perspectives.

Data Gathering Instruments

For the purpose of this study, a researcher-made questionnaire was used to examine the challenges and opportunities experienced by teachers in relation to the implementation of the Expanded Career Progression System for Teachers (ECPS-T) at Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal.

Construction of Questionnaire

The primary instrument for data collection is a researcher-made survey questionnaire, structured according to the research questions. It was divided into sections: (a) teachers' perceptions of opportunities (training, promotion, recognition, skills development), (b) influence on motivation and commitment, (c) balancing ECPS demands with teaching responsibilities, and (d) challenges encountered (workload, requirements, evaluation system, career mobility).

Validation of the Questionnaire

After seeking approval of the topic done by the professor in this course, the questionnaire was submitted to practitioners for their review and comments. After soliciting their comments, these were incorporated and included in the final copy to be given to the participants. Initially, the researcher asked for consultation with the school principal of Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal and Master Teachers for correction, comments and suggestion of the questionnaire.

Administration of the Questionnaire

The researcher sent a letter of request to the school principal of Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal for the administration of the questionnaire. Upon approval, the questionnaire was administered to the participants. Confidentiality and voluntary participation were emphasized. Retrieval. The questionnaire was retrieved after the participants finished answering them.

Data Analysis

The study employed a descriptive research design, utilizing a structured questionnaire distributed among 40 teachers of Paaralang Elementarya ng Marcal. Weighted mean and ranking were used to analyze the data. The results were based on the ranges below with corresponding verbal interpretation.

Option	Scale Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50-3.49	Agree
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree

3. Results

Table 1.1
Teachers' Perception on the Opportunities provided by the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) for their Professional Growth in Terms of Training

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
A. Training			
<i>I believe that through ECPS...</i>			
1. teachers will be provided with adequate training programs.	3.7872	Strongly Agree	4
2. trainings provided were aligned with teachers' professional development needs.	3.6596	Strongly Agree	7
3. teachers were encouraged to participate in seminars and workshops.	3.8298	Strongly Agree	2
4. teachers were given easy access to relevant and updated training opportunities.	3.5532	Strongly Agree	8
5. provision of training improves teachers' classroom performance.	3.3404	Agree	10
6. teachers have the freedom to choose the training that will best fit their interests.	3.7234	Strongly Agree	5
7. teachers' training, regardless of the level, can be used for reclassification.	3.8085	Strongly Agree	3
8. required number of hours of training will no longer be a burden.	3.5106	Strongly Agree	9
9. teachers were given equal opportunities to attend different trainings.	3.7021	Strongly Agree	6
10. trainings will not affect the teaching hours of the teachers.	3.5723	Strongly Agree	1

Table 1 presents the teachers' perception of the opportunities provided by the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) in terms of training. The results indicate that teachers generally have a highly positive perception, as reflected by the overall "Strongly Agree" interpretation. The findings suggest that ECPS effectively promotes access to professional development opportunities, encourages participation in seminars and workshops, and allows teachers to utilize training for career advancement such as reclassification. Notably, teachers appreciate that training opportunities do not significantly interfere with their teaching hours, which highlights the system's consideration of instructional responsibilities. Additionally, respondents agree that ECPS provides equal opportunities for teachers to attend relevant and updated training programs, fostering inclusivity and professional growth. However, the indicator stating that training improves classroom performance received the lowest mean, although still within the "Agree" range. This suggests that while teachers value the availability of training, some may still be uncertain about its direct impact on classroom practices. Overall, the results imply that ECPS serves as a strong support mechanism for continuous professional development, although further alignment between training programs and classroom application may enhance its effectiveness.

Table 1.2
Teachers' Perception on the Opportunities provided by the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) for their Professional Growth in Terms of Promotion

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
B. Promotion			
<i>I believe that ECPS...</i>			
1. opens more opportunities for career advancement.	3.6870	Strongly Agree	3
2. promotion process under is transparent and fair.	3.5592	Strongly Agree	7
3. motivates me to apply for higher positions.	3.5255	Strongly Agree	8
4. promotion opportunities encourage me to enhance my competencies.	3.6530	Strongly Agree	5
5. inspires me to remain steadfast in the teaching profession.	3.7405	Strongly Agree	1
6. provides equal promotion opportunities to teachers regardless of their school assignment.	3.6230	Strongly Agree	6
7. promotion criteria are clearly communicated to all teachers.	3.4085	Agree	9
8. provides enough time for teachers to prepare the needed requirements.	2.2100	Disagree	10
9. recognizes teachers' achievements and contributions as part of promotion evaluation.	3.7025	Strongly Agree	2
10. enhances teachers' sense of professional fulfillment and career satisfaction.	3.6723	Strongly Agree	4

Table 2 shows the teachers' perception of the opportunities provided by ECPS in terms of promotion. The findings reveal that teachers strongly agree that ECPS offers meaningful opportunities for career advancement and professional growth. The highest-rated responses indicate that the system inspires teachers to remain committed to the teaching profession and recognizes their achievements and contributions as part of the promotion process. This suggests that ECPS functions as a motivating factor that enhances teachers' morale and professional satisfaction. Teachers also perceive that promotion opportunities encourage them to improve their competencies and pursue higher positions, indicating the system's role in fostering a growth-oriented mindset. Furthermore, respondents agree that the promotion process is generally transparent and fair, contributing to a positive perception of the system's credibility. However, the lowest-rated indicator, which pertains to the sufficiency of time given to prepare promotion requirements, received a "Disagree" rating. This implies that teachers may experience difficulty in meeting deadlines and managing requirements, highlighting a potential area for improvement. Overall, the results suggest that while ECPS effectively promotes career advancement, adjustments in timelines and support mechanisms are necessary to enhance its implementation.

Table 1.3
Teachers' Perception on the Opportunities provided by the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) for their Professional Growth in Terms of Recognition

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
C. Recognition			
<i>I believe that ECPS...</i>			
1. recognizes teachers' professional contributions.	3.8875	Strongly Agree	1
2. makes us feel valued because of the recognition opportunities provided.	3.7596	Strongly Agree	2
3. motivates me to do my best in teaching to be recognized.	3.4292	Agree	10
4. initiatives make my efforts properly acknowledged.	3.5532	Strongly Agree	7
5. highlights diverse teacher accomplishments (teaching, leadership, specialization).	3.5400	Strongly Agree	8
6. ensures that recognition is based on merit and performance, not seniority alone.	3.6234	Strongly Agree	4
7. provides equal recognition opportunities for teachers across all grade levels and subject areas.	3.7085	Strongly Agree	3
8. motivates me to innovate and use creative strategies in teaching to gain recognition.	2.5105	Agree	9
9. acknowledges teachers who contribute to community and learner development beyond classroom teaching.	3.6022	Strongly Agree	5
10. strengthens my professional identity and sense of belonging within the teaching community.	3.5723	Strongly Agree	6

In terms of teachers' perception on the opportunities provided by the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) for their Professional growth in terms of recognition, teachers strongly agree that ECPS provides meaningful opportunities for recognition and appreciation of their professional contributions.

The highest-rated indicator highlights that ECPS helps affirm teachers' efforts and dedication to their work. This suggests that recognition plays a vital role in motivating teachers to sustain and improve their performance. Similarly, teachers agreed that ECPS makes them feel valued and ensures fairness in recognition, reflecting the system's perceived equity and transparency.

Table 1.4
Teachers' Perception on the Opportunities provided by the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) for their Professional Growth in Terms of Skills Development

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
D. Skills Development			
<i>I believe that ECPS...</i>			
1. encourages me to improve my teaching skills.	3.8772	Strongly Agree	1
2. helps me acquired new strategies due to its requirements.	3.8596	Strongly Agree	2
3. supports my continuous professional learning.	3.8295	Strongly Agree	3
4. develops my confidence as a teacher.	3.6532	Strongly Agree	5
5. helps me become more competent in the field.	3.5404	Strongly Agree	7
6. encourages me to pursue advanced training and specialization to improve my teaching skills.	3.8230	Strongly Agree	4
7. enhances my ability to integrate technology and innovative strategies in instruction.	3.6085	Strongly Agree	6
8. promotes collaboration and knowledge sharing among colleagues for skills improvement.	3.5102	Strongly Agree	8
9. allows me to reflect on and improve my teaching practices through feedback and evaluation.	3.2521	Agree	10
10. develops my leadership and mentoring skills as part of professional growth.	2.5720	Agree	9

The data in Table 1.4 reveal that teachers strongly agree that the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) significantly contributes to their skills development. The highest-rated indicator suggests that ECPS motivates teachers to enhance their instructional practices continually. Other top-rated indicators, such as “helps me acquire new strategies due to its requirements” and “supports my continuous professional learning” emphasize ECPS’s role in promoting professional growth through training and exposure to innovative teaching methods.

Part II: Influence on Motivation and Commitment

Table 2.1
 Influence of Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS)
 to teachers' motivation and commitment to teaching
 profession in terms of Implementation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
A. Implementation			
<i>I believe that...</i>			
1. ECPS is effectively introduced in our school.	3.5882	Strongly Agree	4
2. ECPS guidelines are clear and accessible.	3.7595	Strongly Agree	2
3. I am well-informed about the requirements.	3.4290	Agree	8
4. The implementation process is manageable for teachers.	2.5534	Agree	10
5. The administration supports the implementation of ECPS.	3.8404	Strongly Agree	1
6. ECPS implementation is consistent across all grade levels and subject areas	3.5232	Strongly Agree	5
7. School heads provide sufficient guidance and monitoring during the implementation of ECPS.	3.7084	Strongly Agree	3
8. There are orientation and capacity-building activities conducted to support ECPS implementation.	3.5105	Strongly Agree	6
9. Teachers are involved in the planning and decision-making process related to ECPS implementation.	2.7021	Agree	9
10. Feedback mechanisms are in place to improve the implementation of ECPS.	3.4723	Agree	7

The results presented in Table 2.1 indicate that teachers have a generally positive perception of the implementation of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS), with an overall interpretation of Strongly Agree. The highest-rated indicator reflects strong institutional backing and leadership support, which are essential in ensuring the system's successful rollout. Similarly, indicators such as "ECPS guidelines are clear and accessible" and "School heads provide sufficient guidance and monitoring during the implementation" suggest that the dissemination of information and administrative assistance are well in place.

However, indicators like "The implementation process is manageable for teachers" and "Teachers are involved in the planning and decision-making process" received lower weighted means, indicating that some educators may still feel burdened by procedural demands or lack participatory involvement.

Table 2.2
 Influence of Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS)
 to teachers' motivation and commitment to teaching
 profession in terms of Teachers' Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
B. Teachers' Motivation			
<i>I believe that...</i>			
1. ECPS motivates me to enhance my teaching performance.	3.6870	Strongly Agree	5
2. The opportunities under ECPS increase my job satisfaction.	3.5986	Strongly Agree	8
3. I am inspired to pursue higher studies because of ECPS.	3.7278	Strongly Agree	2
4. ECPS motivates me to innovate in my teaching practices.	3.6542	Strongly Agree	6
5. My enthusiasm for teaching has improved due to ECPS.	3.5410	Agree	9
6. ECPS increases my confidence in performing my teaching duties effectively.	3.6235	Strongly Agree	7
7. The ECPS inspires me to set higher professional goals.	3.7084	Strongly Agree	4
8. ECPS motivates teachers to achieve all observable indicators in the COI.	3.7105	Strongly Agree	3
9. I feel more valued and appreciated in my profession because of ECPS.	3.5012	Strongly Agree	10
10. ECPS encourages me to accomplish all NCOI ahead of time.	3.8723	Strongly Agree	1

Table 2.2 presents the influence of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) on teachers' motivation. The results show that teachers strongly agree that ECPS enhances their motivation and professional drive, as reflected in the high overall weighted means.

The top-rated indicator reveals that teachers are highly motivated to meet and even exceed performance standards. Similarly, the indicators "I am inspired to pursue higher studies because of ECPS" and "ECPS motivates teachers to achieve all observable indicators in the COI" indicate that ECPS effectively stimulates teachers' ambition for professional growth and goal attainment. Although indicator 9 ranked lowest, it still falls under the Agree interpretation, implying overall positive motivational impact.

Table 2.3

Influence of Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS)
to teachers' motivation and commitment to teaching
profession in terms of Professional Commitment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
2.3 Professional Commitment			
<i>I believe that...</i>			
1. I remain committed to my profession despite ECPS demands.	3.7842	Strongly Agree	3
2. the ECPS strengthens my dedication as a teacher.	3.8595	Strongly Agree	2
3. my loyalty to the teaching profession is influenced positively by ECPS.	3.8890	Strongly Agree	1
4. I am more willing to accept professional responsibilities under ECPS.	2.5532	Agree	10
5. my sense of purpose as a teacher is reinforced by ECPS.	3.4404	Agree	6
6. ECPS motivates me to uphold the standards and ethics of the teaching profession.	3.7433	Strongly Agree	4
7. I take greater pride in my role as an educator because of ECPS.	3.4084	Agree	7
8. ECPS encourages me to remain in the teaching profession despite challenges.	3.3206	Agree	8
9. I feel more accountable for my professional performance under ECPS.	3.2024	Agree	9
10. ECPS inspires me to pursue long-term goals and career growth within the teaching profession.	3.6725	Strongly Agree	5

This table illustrates the influence of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) on teachers' professional commitment. The results reveal that teachers generally exhibit a strong commitment to their profession as influenced by ECPS, as reflected in the high weighted means and overall "Strongly Agree" interpretation. The top-rated statement signifies that ECPS fosters a sense of allegiance and pride among educators. This is followed by "The ECPS strengthens my dedication as a teacher" and "I remain committed to my profession despite ECPS demands" which indicate that the system enhances teachers' resilience and devotion to their work.

Meanwhile, the lowest-rated indicator, "I am more willing to accept professional responsibilities under ECPS", though still Agree, suggests that some teachers may experience workload concerns that slightly affect their willingness to take on added tasks.

Part III: Balancing ECPS Demands and Teaching Responsibilities

Table 3
Teachers Balance the Demands of the (ECPS)
with their Classroom Responsibilities

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>I believe that...</i>			
1. I balance ECPS tasks and teaching responsibilities through a prioritization strategy.	3.7842	Strongly Agree	2
2. my teaching duties remain my priority despite ECPS.	3.8565	Strongly Agree	1
3. I manage my time effectively to balance ECPS and classroom responsibility.	3.6290	Strongly Agree	5
4. I am not allowing the system to compromise my classroom performance.	3.6530	Strongly Agree	4
5. I receive support from colleagues to balance responsibilities.	3.2405	Agree	10
6. ECPS tasks sometimes conflict with teaching duties.	3.7254	Strongly Agree	3
7. balancing ECPS and teaching is manageable for me.	2.5885	Agree	6
8. the system requires careful time management.	3.5104	Strongly Agree	8
9. I can fulfill ECPS requirements without sacrificing teaching quality.	3.5021	Strongly Agree	9
10. support systems help me balance ECPS and teaching work.	3.5723	Strongly Agree	7

Table 3 presents the teachers' perception of how they balance the demands of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) with their classroom responsibilities. The overall results reveal a strongly positive perception among teachers, indicating their capacity to manage ECPS requirements alongside their teaching roles.

The highest-rated indicator suggests that teachers consistently uphold instructional quality and learner outcomes as their foremost responsibility. This is closely followed by "I balance ECPS tasks and teaching responsibilities through a prioritization strategy" and "ECPS tasks sometimes conflict with teaching duties", which reflect the balancing act educators face—acknowledging the challenges while demonstrating commitment to both professional development and classroom performance. Meanwhile, the lowest-rated indicator implies that collegial and institutional support mechanisms could be further strengthened to promote effective workload management.

Part IV: Challenges Encountered in ECPS

Table 4
Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of ECPS
In relation to their Teaching Profession

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
4.1 Workload		
<i>I believe that...</i>		
1. ECPS increases my workload significantly.	2.1870	Disagree
2. Workload becomes overwhelming under ECPS.	2.3596	Disagree
3. My teaching performance is affected by ECPS workload.	3.7298	Strongly Agree
4. I spend extra hours to complete ECPS tasks.	3.8532	Strongly Agree
5. Additional ECPS workload affects my work-life balance.	3.5404	Strongly Agree
4.2 Requirements		
6. Requirements of ECPS are difficult to accomplish.	3.8405	Strongly Agree
7. Documentary requirements consume much time.	3.7254	Strongly Agree
8. I need more guidance to comply with requirements.	3.8532	Strongly Agree
9. Some requirements are unclear and confusing.	2.3596	Disagree
10. Completing requirements affects my teaching time.	2.4596	Disagree
4.3 Evaluation System		
<i>I believe that...</i>		
11. Evaluation procedures are transparent.	3.7872	Strongly Agree
12. Some aspects of evaluation are difficult to achieve.	2.4596	Disagree
13. Evaluation results are reliable and trustworthy.	3.9298	Strongly Agree
14. Evaluation promotes healthy competition.	3.6532	Strongly Agree
15. ECPS evaluation is fair and objective.	3.7404	Strongly Agree
4.4 Career Mobility		
16. Only highly qualified teachers can advance.	2.4240	Disagree
17. Promotion under ECPS takes a long process.	2.7652	Agree
18. Career mobility is affected by school resources.	2.5445	Agree
19. ECPS has made promotions more competitive.	3.1575	Agree
20. Career progression is more systematic under ECPS.	3.6784	Strongly Agree

Table 4 reveals the challenges experienced by teachers in implementing the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS). The findings show that while teachers strongly agree on several aspects of workload, requirements, and evaluation, there are also areas where they express disagreement, suggesting mixed perceptions of the system's impact.

In terms of workload, teachers strongly agree that ECPS tasks require extra hours and affect their work-life balance, though they disagree that the system significantly increases their workload overall. This indicates that while ECPS does not drastically add to daily teaching tasks, it still demands time and effort outside regular hours. This aligns with Kyriacou (2016), who noted that additional administrative and professional tasks often increase teacher stress even when overall workload appears stable.

Under requirements, teachers strongly agree that ECPS requirements are difficult to accomplish and that they need more guidance. They also find documentary demands time-consuming. This suggests a need for clearer communication and technical support during implementation. Similarly, OECD (2019) found that excessive administrative demands can detract from instructional quality and teacher motivation.

For the evaluation system, teachers strongly agree that evaluation procedures are transparent and that results are reliable and trustworthy. They also view evaluation as promoting healthy competition. These results imply that teachers perceive ECPS evaluation as generally fair and constructive. This agrees with Darling-Hammond (2015), who emphasized that effective evaluation systems enhance teacher professionalism when transparency and fairness are maintained.

Regarding career mobility, teachers agree that promotion under ECPS is a long process and influenced by school resources. Nonetheless, they strongly agree that career progression under ECPS is now more systematic. This finding resonates with Hargreaves and Fullan (2020), who argue that structured career pathways can foster professional growth when educators perceive them as attainable and merit based.

Part V: Guide for the Development of School-Level Support Systems for the Effective Implementation of the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS)

The findings of the study reveal that teachers view the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) as a valuable framework for promoting professional growth and enhancing motivation. However, their experiences also highlight several areas where additional support is needed to ensure its effective and sustainable implementation.

Teachers' responses indicate that while they strongly agree that ECPS strengthens their dedication, loyalty, and commitment to the teaching profession, they also face challenges related to workload management, compliance with documentary requirements, and career mobility. Many teachers expressed that the system demands additional time and effort beyond regular teaching duties, and that guidance and administrative assistance are often limited.

These insights suggest the need for school-level support systems that focus on capacity-building, workload balancing, and transparent communication. Schools can develop the following mechanisms based on teachers' experiences:

1. **Coaching and Mentoring Programs** – Assigning master teachers or department heads to guide teachers through ECPS requirements, portfolio preparation, and evaluation processes. This echoes the findings of Darling-Hammond (2013), who emphasized the role of mentorship in supporting professional advancement.
2. **Administrative and Technical Assistance** – Schools should designate focal persons or committees to assist in documentation, digital submission, and interpretation of ECPS guidelines. According to OECD (2019), reducing administrative barriers allows teachers to focus more on instructional quality and professional growth.
3. **Professional Development and Training** – Regular workshops and seminars should be conducted to clarify ECPS standards, evaluation rubrics, and competency expectations. As Hargreaves and Fullan (2012) noted, continuous professional learning strengthens teacher confidence and system alignment.
4. **Workload Adjustment Measures** – School leaders should consider adjusting non-teaching tasks or redistributing responsibilities to ensure teachers can comply with ECPS requirements without compromising classroom instruction. This aligns with Kyriacou's (2011) assertion that managing teacher workload is vital to maintaining motivation and job satisfaction.
5. **Recognition and Incentive Systems** – Establishing recognition programs for teachers who demonstrate excellence or initiative under ECPS can foster morale and encourage a culture of professional growth.

Overall, teachers' lived experiences serve as an essential feedback mechanism for refining ECPS implementation. By listening to their insights, school administrators can design supportive structures that not only ease compliance but also empower teachers to view ECPS as a pathway toward professional empowerment rather than a bureaucratic burden.

4. Discussion

The results of the study indicate that the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) serves as a significant mechanism for enhancing teachers' professional growth, motivation, and commitment. The strong agreement of teachers regarding opportunities in training, promotion, recognition, and skills development supports the idea that structured career progression systems can positively influence teacher performance and job satisfaction. These findings are consistent with existing literature, which emphasizes that access to professional development and recognition plays a crucial role in sustaining teacher motivation and improving instructional practices.

The positive influence of ECPS on teacher motivation and commitment can be attributed to its competency-based framework, which rewards effort, achievement, and professional growth. When teachers perceive that their contributions are acknowledged and that clear pathways for advancement exist, they are more likely to invest in their professional development and remain committed to their roles. This aligns with motivational theories that highlight the importance of recognition and career advancement in enhancing job satisfaction and performance.

However, the challenges identified in the study highlight important considerations for the effective implementation of ECPS. The need to balance teaching responsibilities with ECPS-related tasks suggests that teachers may experience role strain, particularly when administrative demands increase. The difficulty in complying with documentary requirements further indicates that while the system promotes accountability, it may also create additional burdens if not properly supported. These findings underscore the importance of providing adequate administrative assistance, clear communication, and structured support systems to ensure that teachers can meet ECPS requirements without compromising their primary role as educators.

Moreover, the perception of fairness and transparency in the evaluation system is a positive indicator of the system's credibility. When teachers trust the evaluation process, they are more likely to engage actively in professional development activities and strive for improvement. However, the concerns related to workload and preparation time suggest that implementation strategies must be carefully designed to balance accountability with practicality.

Overall, the study highlights that while ECPS is a promising reform, its success depends on how well it is implemented at the school level. Effective leadership, continuous support, and collaborative practices are essential in ensuring that the system benefits teachers without creating unnecessary stress or challenges.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the following are hereby concluded.

1. The study concludes that the Expanded Career Progression System (ECPS) has positively influenced teachers' motivation and professional commitment. Teachers strongly agree that ECPS inspires them to improve their teaching performance, pursue higher studies, and set higher professional goals, showing that the system effectively promotes career growth and job satisfaction.
2. Despite its benefits, teachers encounter challenges related to increased workload, documentary requirements, and the complexity of evaluation processes. These factors can lead to stress and reduced time for classroom preparation, indicating a need for balanced implementation strategies at the school level.
3. Teachers' experiences emphasize the importance of mentoring, administrative assistance, and clear communication regarding ECPS policies and expectations. Without these, the potential of ECPS to enhance professional growth may be undermined by confusion or burnout.
4. The findings highlight that schools with stronger collegial support and leadership engagement experience smoother ECPS implementation. This suggests that professional collaboration and shared accountability are essential for sustaining motivation and performance under ECPS.
5. Continuous monitoring and policy refinement of the ECPS are essential to address emerging challenges, maintain fairness in promotion processes, and align the system with the evolving needs of teachers and the educational landscape.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended.

1. **Establish a School-Based ECPS Support Committee.**

Create a team composed of master teachers, department heads, and administrators to

provide coaching, mentoring, and technical assistance to teachers in preparing and submitting ECPS-related requirements.

2. Conduct Regular Orientation and Capacity-Building Programs.

Schools should organize continuous professional development sessions focusing on ECPS guidelines, evaluation standards, and documentation procedures to ensure all teachers are well-informed and confident in the process.

3. Enhance Communication and Transparency.

Provide clear and timely information on ECPS evaluation criteria, timelines, and feedback mechanisms. Open dialogue between teachers and administrators can build trust and reduce misconceptions.

4. Recognize and Reward Professional Growth.

Schools may introduce recognition or incentive programs for teachers who demonstrate exemplary performance, innovation, or commitment under ECPS. Acknowledgment of achievements reinforces motivation and professional pride.

5. Strengthen Peer Collaboration and Sharing of Best Practices.

Encourage teachers to engage in learning communities or peer mentoring sessions where they can exchange strategies for balancing ECPS requirements with teaching responsibilities.

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